

Can Buckminsterfullerene be treated as an Atom?

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In recent years there has been tremendous upsurge of interest¹ in the study of carbon clusters especially C₆₀ popularly known as Buckminsterfullerene. The importance of C₆₀ is due to its extraordinary stability as has been observed in the corresponding mass spectrum². It may be considered³ to be a consequence of a maximum hardness principle⁴. The structure of C₆₀ is proposed⁵ to be a highly symmetric icosahedral arrangement of sixty identical carbon atoms each of which is shared by one pentagonal and two hexagonal faces. Various experiments supported this structure⁶.

The exceptional stability of C₆₀ vis-a-vis its novel structure in which sixty carbon atoms are uniformly distributed on the surface of a hypothetical sphere prompted experimentalists⁶ as well as theoreticians^{7,8} in understanding structure, properties and reactivity of it. Calculations^{7,8} have been performed both at the semi-empirical and *ab initio* levels. In this presentation we would like to envisage an atomic model for the electronic structure calculation of C₆₀.

Let us consider a spherical shell of radius r_c on which 360 units of positive charge is uniformly smeared out and 360 electrons are moving under the potential due to this charge distribution. In the limit of r_c going to zero this system reduces to an atom with atomic number 360. Therefore, the electronic structure can be obtained through the numerical solution of Schrödinger equation, Hartree-Fock equation or Euler-Lagrange equation in density functional theory for an atom ($Z = 360$) with a slightly different form for the external potential due to

electron-nuclear attraction. This form can be obtained from Gauss's law as follows:

$$V(r) = \begin{cases} -\frac{360}{r_c}, & r \leq r_c \\ -\frac{360}{r}, & r > r_c \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

It is hoped that this central potential will allow us to treat C₆₀ (like an isolated atom) as a member of the full rotation group such that its electronic structure can be expressed in terms of the quantum numbers n , l and m_l or their variants.

In what follows, the system is composed of two different solvable quantum mechanical problems. Inside the spherical shell it is a problem of 'particle in a spherical box' with a finite boundary potential (albeit attractive) such that particles can penetrate the wall. Outside the shell it is a typical atomic problem with standard coulomb potential. Radius of the sphere (r_c) may be given as an input obtainable from experiment⁶ or may be used as a variational parameter in a self-consistent calculation.

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